

THEORIES OF DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE TEACHER'S
METAMETHODICAL COMPETENCE

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Annotation: This article analyzes the problem of developing universal educational activities of future teachers and identifies the main types of universal educational activities. The main concepts and theories in the framework of the problem of formation of metamethodical competence in students are pedagogically interpreted.

Keywords: Pedagogical activity, education, metamethodic competence, universal educational actions, types of universal educational actions.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarning universal ta’lim faoliyatini rivojlantirish muammosi tahlil etilgan hamda universal ta’lim harakatlarining asosiy turlari aniqlashtirilgan. Talabalarda metamethodik kompetentlikni shakllantirish muammosi doirasidagi asosiy tushuncha va nazariyalar pedagogik talqin etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Pedagogik faoliyat, ta’lim, metamethodik kompetentlik, universal ta’lim harakatlari, universal ta’lim harakatlari turlari.

The global processes taking place in the world require rapid improvement of the education and training space, determination of educational goals that take into account the needs and interests of the state, society and the individual. In this regard, the design of universal educational activities aimed at the main results of education and which students should master in higher education institutions acquires actual scientific and practical importance. The development of students in the educational system is ensured, first of all, by the formation of universal

(metasubject) educational activities, which are the invariant basis of the educational and educational process. Successful independent acquisition of comprehensive educational activities by students, i.e. new knowledge, skills and abilities, creates an opportunity to effectively organize this process.

Today, one of the main tasks is to prepare the graduates of elementary schools of general education to be able to effectively perform various organizational, independent learning and communicative tasks based on social requirements. There was a need for targeted training of future teachers for this activity. Therefore, the development of metamethodical competence of future primary education teachers is of urgent theoretical and practical importance.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", "On measures to further develop the field of pedagogical education" and "Uzbekistan In the decrees and decisions on approving the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic until 2030, "Higher education is the state education standard. Basic rules, classification of higher education directions and specialties" by forming universal knowledge in students, teaching them to imagine the world as a whole, to think creatively and critically, to develop the personality of the student, to the formation of skills to demonstrate their capabilities was defined as a priority task.

In students L.F. Kvitova, K.Yu. Kolesina, MR in scientific works of Leonteva; issues of formation of metasubject skills that allow students to find options for solving social problems O.Ye. By. Lebedeva, PG Shedrovskys; some aspects of developing students' metamethodical competences based on the competence approach were researched by B.A. Takhokhov, M.I. Bekoeva, Z.K. Malieva.

Concepts such as metasubjectivity, metamethodology, metamethodical approach, and metamethodical competence are not fully disclosed in the scientific and pedagogical literature.

Some researchers, including Yu.V. Gromko interprets the concept of metasubjectivity as "pre-subjectivity", that is, activity-oriented didactics.

A.V. Khutorskoy in his opinion, metasubjects are fundamental educational objects [1].

scientific and pedagogical literature, metamethodology describes integration processes in order to form a holistic view of the world in students during the educational process. is a new direction of research methodology said views are also available (I.V. Blauberg, L. Bertalanfi, G. Sheffer, NV Gruzdeva, A.Ya. Danilkj, I.D Zverev, V.N Maksimova, G.A. Monakhova, etc.). Thus, metamethodology is different of students while keeping the specific features of teaching methods of different subjects age It consists of the mutual integration that is taken into account.

This in a sense of metamethodology integrative-content and organizational-active aspects are highlighted. First Metamethodology is different within the aspect ways of forming a holistic view of the world in students based on the integration of the content and basic concepts of teaching methods of different subjects, i.e. theoretical and methodological process the basics and practical-methodical aspects researches. In pedagogy until the end of this task solution not done . The same at the time this of the problem some aspects integrated organization of courses issues dedicated its expression in research finding, various by selecting concepts common to different disciplines and integrating them depends there are also studies [2].

To metamethodology known to methods dependent but not them combined, existing in parallel with didactics, of teaching common methodological principles

forming and teaching problems there are also views as a science with its own methods of learning.

In the scientific research that is being carried out today universal learning activities in metamethodology focus on classification given to the students their formation, future teachers this purposeful preparation for the process issues on A.G. Asmolov, G.V. Burmenskaya, I.A. Volodarsky, S.G. Vorovshikov, A.T. Nurmanov such as modern researchers research take are going

In particular, universal educational activities are as follows by A.G. Asmolov classified and recognized by many made: personal, regulatory (reg), related to knowledge and communicative universal learning activities [2].

A.B. Khutorskoy cognitive (related to knowledge), creative (creative), related to organizational activity (methodological), communicative and valuable (worldview) universal learning activities suggests [3].

Content, innovative methods and technologies, pedagogical conditions and practical- technological conditions of development of metamethodical competences in future primary education teacher's aspects in the science of pedagogy enough level research not done. The same currently in the world's leading higher education organizations and scientific centers scientific projects on the development of universal educational activities, i.e. metamethodical competences of future teachers of the process methodological aspects and models are being developed .

In the course of our research, universal educational activities based on this methodology nomenclature determined their psychological content and formation in the educational process to the roads common description was given. Universal educational activities types differentiate the following as criteria defined: functions, structure and form, emergence features, that's it including organization of educational activities conditions.

As a result of the analysis, the main types of universal educational actions determined:

- personal universal actions (self - destiny himself definition, formation of values, ethical and moral evaluation movement);
- regulatory - regulation universal action (goal formation, planning, control make, fix, evaluate, predict do);
- cognitive universal actions (related to knowledge, independent knowledge acquisition with dependent);
- communicative universal actions .

A personal arrangement typical for students of primary school age, cognitive and communicative universal educational activities forms, conditions and factors of their development in the educational process Based on the determination, it is possible to develop psychological -pedagogical recommendations on the organization of their formation, taking into account the content of education it has been.

Marked as a result of the implementation of tasks a program aimed at forming universal educational actions in students for future primary education teachers was developed and pilot-tested practice in the process of work was introduced. This implementation of the program start drinking effectiveness of the educational process in classes increases scientific hypothesis before pushed.

Metamethodical competencies in future teachers “Technology of formation of metamethodical (universal) learning actions in primary school students” aimed at development includes, on the one hand, primary goals and tasks, methods, forms and means of forming universal learning actions in students cover if, the second on the other hand, the future starter class teachers this to the stream training, formation and development of metamethodical competencies in them directed.

The goal of teaching the elective subject "Technology of forming metamethodical (universal) studies in primary school students" is to form

metamethodical competence in future primary education teachers, that is, to prepare them for primary school education. to prepare students for the process of forming universal educational actions, to ensure the implementation of this process.

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